

The Policy Implementation Analysis of Inflation Control in Sukabumi Municipality

(Implementation of Municipal Decree Number 188.45/39-EkBang Dan KD/ 2018 In Sukabumi Municipality)

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Abstract

Controlling inflation requires cross-agency cooperation and coordination between the government at both the central and regional levels and Bank Indonesia. Strengthening coordination in order to achieve low and stable inflation is the background for the formation of the Regional Inflation Control Team (TPID). TPID was first formed in Sukabumi City in 2011. Efforts to achieve TPID's goals were achieved through implementing an inflation control roadmap with the 4K key strategy, namely price affordability, supply availability, smooth distribution and effective communication. The conformity of inflation achievement with the target is one measure of the success of implementing inflation control policies. In the last fourteen years, six periods of Sukabumi City's actual inflation were within Bank Indonesia's inflation target, while in the other eight years actual inflation was below or above the target. as many as 6 periods, this research uses a descriptive method with a qualitative approach. Data collection techniques through interviews, observation and documentation studies. The research objects were members of the Sukabumi City TPID and West Java Province TPID resource persons. The implementation of the inflation control policy in Sukabumi City is running effectively because the policy standards and targets have been integrated into the development planning program and won an award for the best performance in controlling regional inflation in 2021. The implementing human resources show good quality and are very supportive. However, supporting facilities and infrastructure still need special attention. The TPID implementing organization is a bureaucracy that complies with the legality of existing laws. Communication between related organizations is running well according to communication progress. The current social, economic and political environment is favorable. Effectiveness will increase if it is supported by a budget, infrastructure facilities, increased insight of the parties involved, and a complete inflation control intervention program. Policies need to continue to be updated to be adaptive to dynamic developments in economic phenomena.

Keywords: policy implementation, inflation, stable data.

Introduction

The city of Sukabumi has a strategic geographical location on the route between the capital of West Java province and the capital of Indonesia, supported by adequate facilities and infrastructure. The development of Sukabumi City has now entered the fourth stage of the 2005-2025 Regional Long Term Development Plan (RPJPD) for Sukabumi City, which is characterized

by competitive economic power and integration between the service and agricultural sectors. In line with the 2018-2023 Regional Medium Term Development Plan (RJPMMD) in the 3rd mission, namely realizing an advanced regional economy based on the trade, creative economy and tourism sectors through the principle of partnership with the business world, the world of education and the surrounding area for economic activities, especially trade. and services are the focus in the development of Sukabumi City. The superiority of Sukabumi City's economic potential is also taken into account on the national stage, as evidenced by the inclusion of Sukabumi City as one of the 82 regions based on Indonesia's inflation calculations. This means that the economic dynamics of Sukabumi City also determine national conditions.

BPS calculates the Economic Growth Rate (LPE) based on changes in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at the national level or Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) for the provincial and district/city levels, on the basis of periodic constant prices. The high LPE, which is also accompanied by high inflation, has resulted in a minimal impact of development on improving people's welfare. One of the negative sides caused by economic development is inflation.

Figure 1. Sukabumi City Economic Growth and Inflation Rate yoy, 2011-2022 (%)

Source: Sukabumikota.bps.go.id (processed), 2024

During the 2011-2022 period, Sukabumi City's economic growth was in the range of 5 percent. The highest growth was recorded in 2011 at 6.18 percent and the lowest was negative 1.49 percent or what is called a contraction in 2020, during the Covid 19 pandemic. Inflation in the same period was more volatile than the LPE. In general, Sukabumi City's LPE is able to be above the inflation rate every year, only in four years, namely 2013, 2014, 2020 and 2022, the inflation value surpasses the LPE. According to theoretical studies, inflation that is too high will weaken people's purchasing power and result in hampering economic growth, whereas inflation that is too low reflects a sluggish economy with minimal price movements for goods/services resulting in economic stagnation. An inflation rate that is categorized as good is one that maintains stability and is in a value that is balanced with the economic movements that occur.

Bank Indonesia, in its capacity as a central bank, aims to achieve stability in the value of the rupiah, maintain payment system stability and contribute to maintaining financial system stability in order to support sustainable economic growth. Based on Law Number 4 of 2023 concerning the development and strengthening of the financial sector, Bank Indonesia as the monetary authority in Indonesia, implements policies to achieve stability in the value of the rupiah by maintaining the stability of prices of goods and services as well as the rupiah exchange rate. The macroeconomic indicator used to measure price changes is called inflation. Inflation is an increase in the prices of goods and services in general where these goods and services are basic needs of society or a decrease in the selling power of a country's currency (BPS, 2023).

Since 2005, Bank Indonesia has implemented the Inflation Targeting Framework (ITF), by setting a target range for inflation within a period that is explicitly determined to the public. Inflation is a reflection of macroeconomic conditions as assessed by various interested parties, therefore controlling inflation is carried out by setting targets. Determining the inflation target is carried out using projections from a number of economic models and various available information to describe economic conditions that will occur in the future, and periodically evaluates its suitability to the targets set.

Table 1. Inflation Target and Actual Inflation (yoy) Sukabumi City and West Java Province, 2010-2023 (%)

Year	Inflation Target	Sukabumi City Actual Inflation	West Java Actual Inflation
2010	5±1	5.43	6.62
2011	5±1	4.26	3.10
2012	4.5±1	3.98	3.86
2013	4.5±1	8.03	9.15
2014	4.5±1	8.38	7.41
2015	4±1	2.20	2.73
2016	4±1	2.57	2.75
2017	4±1	4.1	3.63
2018	3.5±1	2.95	3.54
2019	3.5±1	2.33	3.21
2020	3±1	1.84	2.18
2021	3±1	1.71	1.69
2022	3±1	5.45	6.04
2023	3±1	3.03	2.85

Source: <https://www.bi.go.id> and <https://sukabumikota.bps.go.id> (processed)

Based on data for the last 14 (fourteen) years, the highest inflation rate for Sukabumi City was 8.83 percent which occurred in 2014, while the lowest was experienced in 2021 at 1.71 percent. The spike in inflation rates tends to be caused by government policy to increase the

prices of regulated goods/services, such as fuel oil (BBM) and electricity. In 2013-2014, it was recorded that there was a government policy to increase subsidized fuel prices and reduce electricity subsidies, both of these events were reflected in high inflation rates in both years. A similar thing happened in 2017 and 2022 where inflation moved quite high due to the push from fuel price adjustments at that time. The increase in fuel prices has a derivative impact in triggering changes in the prices of various other goods and services, considering that fuel is a component that is used in almost all aspects of life, especially those related to transportation activities.

A comparison of the inflation target set by Bank Indonesia with the inflation experienced by Sukabumi City is presented in table 1.1. During the observation period, actual inflation in line with the target occurred in six years, namely 2010, 2011, 2012, 2017, 2018 and 2023. Meanwhile, in the other eight years, actual inflation exceeded or was lower than the set target. Data shows that there is a mismatch between the targets that have been set and actual inflation. Even though controlled inflation plays an important role in development.

The inflation control mandate carried out by Bank Indonesia is carried out with cross-agency cooperation and coordination, namely with the Government. At the central level, the formation of the Inflation Monitoring and Control Team (TPI) has been in place since 2005. More optimal strengthening of coordination was achieved through the formation of the Regional Inflation Control Team (TPID) which started in 2008 and the number of districts/cities that have TPID continues to increase with rapidly along with awareness of the importance of controlling inflation. The legal umbrella for the formation and management of TPID is based on the Presidential Decree (Kepres) of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 of 2017 dated 8 August 2017 concerning the National Inflation Control Team. All provinces and districts/cities were ordered to form inflation control teams in their respective regions no later than 60 days after the Presidential Decree was issued. The City of Sukabumi responded by issuing Mayor's Decree No. 35 of 2017 concerning the Establishment of a Regional Inflation Control Team for the City of Sukabumi, which was then revoked and updated with Mayor of Sukabumi's Decree No. 188.45/39.Ekban&KD/2018 concerning the formation of a Regional Inflation Control Team for the City of Sukabumi. Based on Presidential Decree No. 23 of 2017 article 5 paragraph 2, the district/city TPID is led by the regent/mayor with the deputy chairman as an official from the Bank Indonesia representative office and its members are leaders of regional apparatus organizations related to inflation. The essence of TPID's duties is to collect data on information on prices of goods/services, develop inflation control policies at the district/city level and coordinate with the central and regional governments.

The aim of implementing the inflation control policy in Sukabumi City has not been achieved optimally with differences in actual inflation compared to the targets that have been set. The long journey from the formation of TPID in Sukabumi City to its relevance to controlling inflation in the district and city in a disruptive manner is worth studying. The changing distribution patterns of goods and services along with developments in information and technology and their impact on inflation monitoring and control policies in Sukabumi City are interesting topics to be discussed in more depth.

Based on the background description, the researcher will analyze the implementation of the inflation control policy in Sukabumi City by TPID so that the problems faced can be identified so that later improvements to the policy can be made. The problem formulation in this research is as follows:

1. How is the implementation of the inflation control policy in Sukabumi City by TPID, in terms of dimensions (Van Meter and Van Horn, 1974):
 - Policy standards and targets
 - Resource
 - Characteristics of the implementing organization
 - The attitude of the implementers
 - Communication between related organizations and implementation activities
 - Social, economic and political environment
2. What obstacles hinder the implementation of inflation control policies in Sukabumi City by TPID
3. What efforts must be made to ensure that the implementation of inflation control policies in Sukabumi City by TPID is more effective?

Understanding Public Policy Implementation

Policy implementation is an important stage in the public policy process. No matter how good and good a public policy is made, it will be in vain if there is no effort to implement it because it will not have the desired impact and the goal will not be achieved. This is in accordance with Edwards III's statement (in Akib, 2008:2) that without effective implementation, policy makers' decisions will not be successfully implemented.

Based on this, policy implementation means the implementation of a policy or a way for the policy to achieve its objectives. Implementation is also an effort/activity carried out by policy implementers to obtain results that are in accordance with the goals or objectives of the policy itself. Wibawa (in Akib, 2008:2) the policy implementation stage can be characterized and differentiated from the policy making stage. On the one hand, policy making is a process that has a bottom-up logic, meaning that the policy process begins with conveying aspirations, requests or support from the community. Meanwhile, policy implementation on the other hand has a top-down logic, in the sense of reducing abstract or macro policy alternatives to concrete or micro actions.

Understanding Public Policy

Whether we realize it or not, we often hear the term public policy in everyday social life. Many limitations, concepts and definitions have been proposed regarding what is meant by public policy. Eyestone (in Winarno, 2007: 15) defines public policy as "the relationship between government units and their environment". Many parties and scientists think that this definition is still too broad to understand, because what is meant by public policy according to Eyestone can cover many things.

There are several experts and scientists who define public policy as actions taken by the government in response to a situation, especially those involving public issues. One of them is Parker (in Wahab, 2011: 46) providing a definition that public policy is a specific goal or series of actions carried out by the government at a certain period in relation to a subject or response to a crisis.

Anderson (in Winarno, 2008:20-21) provides limitations regarding public policy as policies developed by government agencies and officials, where the implications of these policies are:

- 1) Public policy always has certain goals or has goal-oriented actions;
- 2) Public policy contains actions carried out by the government;
- 3) Public policy is something that the government has done and is doing and is not what it still intends to do; 4) the public policy taken can be positive in the sense that it is government action regarding a particular problem, or negative in the sense that it is the government's decision not to do something; as well as
- 4) Government policy in a positive sense is based on statutory regulations and their derivatives which are binding and coercive.

Inflation

Inflation is a macroeconomic variable that is considered vital in describing economic conditions in a region. Analysis of the amount of inflation that occurs will influence the results of other macro indicators such as economic growth, banking interest rates and the balance of payments. The definition of inflation according to experts is "...a situation in which there is a persistent upward movement in the general private level..." (Hagger, 1997) which simply means that inflation is a general and continuous tendency to increase prices.

"Inflation is a condition of a general and continuous increase in prices" (Mankiw, 2006) The key word that defines inflation is an increase in prices and occurs continuously. The antonym of inflation is called deflation. New Keynesian economic theory reveals that inflation originates from the demand side, supply side and expectations or known as the "Expectation-Augmented Phillips Curve: The explanation of the theory of sources of inflation put forward in the TPID manual is:

- 1) Inflation from the demand side (demand-pull inflation), is inflation that is triggered by demand that exceeds the availability of supply resulting in an increase in prices on the market, where this is driven, among other things, by an increase in domestic demand, an increase in government spending or an increase in export demand. An example of inflation caused by pressure from the demand side is the increase in prices of goods and services before the celebration of religious holidays, such as Eid or Christmas.
- 2) Inflation from supply (Cost-push/supply shock inflation), is an inflationary event that is driven by an increase in the costs of producing goods or services. According to Bank Indonesia, the causes of inflation from the supply side are exchange rate depreciation, the impact of inflation abroad, increases in commodity prices regulated by the government and negative supply shocks. Examples of cases of inflation originating from pressure on the supply side are increases in transportation rates due to increases in fuel prices (goods whose value is regulated

by the government) and increases in rice prices due to bad weather resulting in crop failure. In inflation caused by pressure on demand for output of goods/services, there will be an increase in the amount of production and prices/tariffs for output (goods/services produced) will rise before the increase in raw materials. On the other hand, inflation due to supply side pressure will actually experience a decrease in the amount of production of goods/services and an increase in the price of raw materials supporting the production of goods/services will occur before the price of the product is marketed.

- 3) Inflation expectations, where inflation occurs due to the influence of perceptions and expectations of the parties involved in the economy. This subjective perspective can have an impact on people's attitudes in determining consumption choices, investments made by investors and various decisions related to the economy. There are two types of inflation expectations, namely adaptive (backward-looking) inflation expectations and forward-looking inflation expectations. The influence of past experience and previous data is the rationale for adaptive inflation expectations. Meanwhile, the latest information and estimates of future conditions are a reference for understanding forward-looking expectations. Bank Indonesia's determination of the inflation target is a product of forward-looking inflation expectations.

Regional Inflation Control Team (TPID)

Controlling inflation is considered important in economic development and is the responsibility of interested parties. BI as the monetary authority is only able to control the demand side (demand management) in accordance with its authority. Meanwhile, inflation components that are influenced by supply pressures and shocks, namely those included in the non-core inflation group, volatile food and administered prices have a weight of around 40 percent of the total commodity goods and services monitored for inflation calculations. Based on these conditions, controlling inflation in Indonesia requires cooperation and coordination across agencies, namely the Government and Bank Indonesia. The initial step in coordinating inflation control was the formation of an Inflation Control Team (TPI) at the central level in 2005, which consisted of representatives from Bank Indonesia and related technical ministries. At the regional level, this was continued with the formation of the Regional Inflation Control Team (TPID) since 2008, consisting of representatives from Bank Indonesia and elements of the regional government. Strengthening regulations regarding the formation of the National Inflation Control Team is outlined in Presidential Decree (Keppres) Number 23 of 2017. In article 2 of Presidential Decree No. 23 of 2017 explains that the National Inflation Control Team consists of a central inflation control team, provincial regional inflation control teams and district/city regional inflation control teams. An explanation of the district/city Regional Inflation Control Team (TPID) is outlined in article 5 of Presidential Decree no. 23 of 2017. The composition of the district/city TPID membership is determined by the decision of the Regent/Mayor.

The formation of TPID in Sukabumi City was based on the decision of the Mayor of Sukabumi Number 188.45/39-Ekbang&KD/2108. The main tasks of the Sukabumi City TPID are:

- 1) Decide on the policies to be adopted regarding controlling inflation in the Sukabumi City area
- 2) Monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of policies taken regarding regional inflation control in Sukabumi City
- 3) Formulate sectoral policy recommendations related to efforts to maintain the affordability of goods and services in the Sukabumi city area to be followed up by the relevant regional work units (SKPD) in accordance with their respective duties and authorities
- 4) Analyze the sources or potential inflationary pressures in the Sukabumi City area
- 5) Analyzing regional economic problems in the Sukabumi city area that could disrupt price stability and affordability of goods and services
- 6) Carrying out an inventory of data and information on developments in prices of goods and services in general by observing inflation developments in the Sukabumi City area
- 7) Identify and analyze Sukabumi city economic problems that can disrupt the affordability of goods and services in Sukabumi City
- 8) Submit recommendations that can support the formulation and determination of general cost standards related to planning and budgeting as well as minimum wages in the City of Sukabumi
- 9) Carrying out communication, socialization and publication as well as providing advice (moral suasion) to the community regarding things needed in an effort to maintain price stability
- 10) Optimizing and synchronizing policies to overcome the problem of affordability of goods and services through TPID coordination meeting forums, central and regional coordination meetings and TPID national coordination meetings
- 11) Prepare TPID reports every 6 months and submit them to the Governor of West Java

The TPID work program guidelines are outlined in a roadmap for controlling inflation with the aim of:

- Ensure continuity, synchronization and accuracy of TPID work programs with regional characteristics
- Synchronize the work programs of each agency related to controlling inflation both in the medium and long term
- Facilitate the resolution of problems related to inflation control down to the district/city level effectively
- Encourage OPD/related agencies to create program innovations

The general composition of TPID membership according to the Instruction of the Ministry of Home Affairs (Imendagri) Number 027/1696/SJ concerning maintaining the affordability of goods and services in the regions is:

Table 2. Composition of TPID membership

No.	Task Description	Person responsible
1	Director	District head
2	Chairman	regional Secretary
3	Vice Chairman	Head of Bank Indonesia Representative Office
4	Secretary	Assistant to the provincial and district/city secretariat in charge of economics
5	Member	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Head of SKPD in charge of agricultural affairs - Head of SKPD in charge of transportation affairs - Head of SKPD in charge of trade and industrial affairs - Other stakeholder elements

SKPD members of TPID adapt to the characteristics of each region and can indicate priorities for handling inflation in that region.

Framework of Thinking

A framework for thinking is the formation of a research path that is clear and can be accepted logically (Sugiyono, 2017:92). The thinking framework is a conceptual model that is used as a theoretical basis related to the factors in research. According to Sugiyono, research requires a framework of thinking so that it can explain theoretically, and can explain the reasons for the relationship between variables.

The following describes the framework of thinking in this research:

Figure 2. Research framework chart

Source: processed by myself

The main focus of this research is the implementation of inflation control policies by the Sukabumi City inflation control team. Theoretically, Van Meter and Van Horn see that policy implementation is influenced by six dimensions, namely: policy standards and targets, resources, characteristics of the implementing organization, communication between related organizations and implementation activities, and the social, economic and political environment. Researchers will base their research focus on these six things and link them to the policy of Sukabumi Mayor Decree Number 188.45/39-Ekbang&KD/2018 concerning the Establishment of a Sukabumi City Regional Inflation Control Team. The assumption is that if the six dimensions are in good condition, the inflation control carried out by the Sukabumi City TPID will achieve the inflation target value that has been set.

The implementation of inflation control policies by TPID in Sukabumi City is greatly influenced by the harmonization of TPID members in implementing work programs in accordance with the Sukabumi City regional inflation control roadmap. Success in achieving the targeted inflation target is the responsibility of all TPID members. Coordination between TPID members and with TPID at the provincial and national levels must continue to be strengthened to be able to face the challenges of structural economic problems.

Method

The research object will be carried out on policy implementers in the Sukabumi City government who are members of the TPID. The parties that will be used as research objects are elements that are members of the TPID Sukabumi City as well as elements related to controlling inflation in Sukabumi City outside the TPID. The research object is directed at:

- a. Communication between TPID members regarding the implementation of the inflation control program according to the inflation control road map
- b. Coordination of Sukabumi City TPID with TPID Pokjanas in regional inflation control measures
- c. The role of policy implementers from each TPID member in the implementation of inflation control
- d. Resources used by TPID Sukabumi City in the process of controlling inflation.
- e. Commitment to implementing inflation control

Qualitative researchers are researchers who intend to understand the phenomena experienced by research subjects, for example behavior, perceptions, motivations, actions and so on. And by means of descriptions in the form of words and language, in a context, especially natural ones and by utilizing various natural methods (Silalahi, 2009:13).

From the opinion about qualitative research above, it is a basis for sufficient consideration for researchers to use a qualitative approach in this research. With the method of using qualitative research, it is hoped that the research carried out can produce more complete findings or data, so that the objectives of this research can be achieved.

This research will use a combined method of interviews, field observations and documentation studies. Interviews with informants will be carried out using prepared interview guidelines. The interview guide used covers all dimensions and variables to be studied.

Informants who will be used as sources by researchers must represent a variety of interests in order to produce diverse information. The sources of informants selected represent elements within the Sukabumi City TPID membership and elements related to inflation policy but are not members of the Sukabumi City TPID. The following is a table containing the names of informants who will be used as sources.

Table 3. Informant data

No	Informant	Status	Reason	Amount
1	Informant 1	Representative of Bank Indonesia West Java Province Office	As deputy chairman of TPID, he has information and capabilities as the main informant	1 person
2	Informant 2	Economic sub-division in the Regional Economy, Development and Cooperation Sector of Sukabumi City Regional Secretariat	As coordinator of the TPID secretariat, has archives of TPID activity data as the main informant	1 person
3	Informant 3	West Java Province BPS Price and Services Statistics Function	As a TPID consultant at the West Java Province level, he is a figure who has complete information and capabilities as the main informant	1 person
4	Informant 4	Sukabumi City Bappeda	As a member of TPID who represents the policy planning side, he is a figure who has complete information as a key informant	1 person
5	Informant 5	Sukabumi City Department of Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry and Trade	As a TPID member whose job is to monitor price data, he is a figure who has complete information as a key informant	1 person
6	Informant 6	Sukabumi City Food Security, Agriculture and Fisheries Department	As a member of TPID in the field of food producers, he is a figure who has complete information as a key informant	1 person

Source: processed by researchers (2024)

Apart from the names above, it is also possible that in the implementation there will be additional informants both from the service environment itself and from outside the service mentioned above if necessary and based on references and suggestions from the initial informants.

The Policy Implementation Analysis of Inflation Control in Sukabumi Municipality

General Description of Research Objects

The object of the research was carried out on policy implementers who were members of the Regional Inflation Control Team (TPID) of the Sukabumi City Government. TPID was formed as a response to strengthening coordination at the regional level in order to achieve low and stable inflation. At the central level, monitoring and controlling inflation has been carried out since 2005 by a team formed by the Government and Bank Indonesia. Inflation control coordination was extended to the provincial level in 2008. Subsequently, the formation of TPID continued to expand to the district/city level. In order to accommodate the need for a legal umbrella for the establishment of TPID, the Ministry of Home Affairs issued Decree of the Minister of Home Affairs (Kepmendagri) No. 500.05-8315 dated 2 October 2017 concerning "Regional Inflation Control Team". Through this Minister of Home Affairs Decree, The composition of membership, duties, guidance, supervision and financing of provincial TPIDs and city district TPIDs is regulated.

The Sukabumi City Government established Sukabumu Mayor Decree Number 188.45/39-EkBang&KD/2018 dated January 15, 2018, concerning "Establishment of the Sukabumi City Regional Inflation Control Team" as the legal basis for the establishment of the TPID in Sukabumi City in accordance with the direction of the Minister of Home Affairs Decree No. 500.05-8315.

This research will discuss the results of field research based on data obtained by researchers through observations, interviews and documentation regarding the Analysis of the Implementation of Inflation Control in Sukabumi City (Implementation of Kepwal Number 188.45/EkBang & KD/2018 of 2018 in Sukabumi City) which includes several variables, are as follows:

1. Policy Standards and Targets

Policy standards refer to criteria that must be met and serve as a reference for assessing their implementation. Meanwhile, targets refer to what the policy wants to achieve. Policy implementation performance begins with the implementers' understanding of the standards and targets to be achieved. There were four aspects of questions that researchers asked to see how the standards and targets for controlling inflation in Sukabumi City were in the views of its members and related parties: in general, all informants stated that the standards and targets for inflation control policies by TPID were clear, logical and measurable. The first informant answered in detail that:

“You could say it is. By referring to the regulations and legislation related to TPID, especially the roadmap for controlling inflation as well as the latest issues related to economic conditions presented by the central government and BI as a reference for controlling inflation”

The third informant gave a short and concise statement, namely that the existing policy standards and targets were clear, logical and measurable. The second informant's response to this question was to explain at length about his duties at Diskumindag as the person responsible for monitoring price developments and availability of basic commodities in the market. In relation to TPID, he felt that he only carried out daily duties in the department and carried out the directions of the leadership (head of department) who was a member. TPID. The fifth and sixth informants had similar answers, namely that the standards and targets of TPID policies were clearly stated in the regulations which were the legal basis for the formation of TPID, but it was the implementation of the inflation control intervention program which was handed over to each region that needed attention. The fifth respondent further added that the price monitoring application programs that are available, namely SILINDA belonging to TPID West Java Province and SP2KP made by the Department of Industry and Trade of West Java Province, have helped in setting the same standards and work targets for all TPIDs in West Java Province.

Responses to questions about whether existing policy standards and targets were ideal or needed improvement were from the third informant as follows: "The evaluation results reported to TPIN show that the policy standards and targets are good"

The fourth informant answered: "It is not yet ideal, even though periodically meetings have been held nationally, at the city level there have been no special meetings held by the Sukabumi City TPID"

The Sukabumi mayor's decision regarding the formation of the TPID is binding on the Head of Service who is its member and the second informant feel that they have never been involved in activities related to policy making so they cannot respond to this question. According to the first informant, the standards and policies regarding controlling inflation are not yet ideal because the resource conditions of each region are different. The sixth informant's opinion on this question is: "Economic phenomena are dynamic, so the ideal conditions for an economic policy must also continue to adapt to the current dynamics, improvements or revisions to the implementation of economic policies must definitely be carried out over time."

To be able to implement a policy, the parties involved must of course have a clear understanding of the aims and objectives of the policy being issued. Regarding the inflation control policy, all informants stated that the aims and objectives of the inflation policy could be understood. Only the fifth informant had a different response to this question, namely: "Understanding of inflation control policies is felt to be still limited to following instructions, for example the implementation of the SPHP program is carried out without based on data for the action agenda"

Meanwhile, the first informant's response was that with the agenda of regular coordination meetings at the national and provincial levels, an understanding of controlling inflation had clearly conveyed its aims and objectives. Even in 2021, inflation control in Sukabumi City was considered successful by the government so that it received an award in the form of incentive

funds. Excerpt from the answer from the second respondent is as follows: “The inflation policy is understandable. However, there is no specific explanation regarding inflation control policies, what has so far been carried out and understood is carrying out activities at TPID in accordance with the main duties and functions of the Ministry of Trade and Industry, such as monitoring prices, monitoring availability, which is somewhat difficult to understand, namely for policies regarding cooperation with producing regions, because it is at the level implementer (according to the informant) the realization of the form of policy with producing regions is not clear enough to be implemented.”

In line with the second informant, the response from the fourth informant was also similar, namely stating that the TPID policy directions conveyed at the coordination meeting could be understood and then followed in accordance with the main duties and functions of their respective services. The third informant stated that the aims and objectives of the inflation control policy should be understood because it has been mapped into programs and activities in the Regional Apparatus Units (SKPD). More fully, this informant stated that the TPID work reference framework, which is outlined in the inflation control road map, needs to be revised so that it is in line with the programs and activities of regional apparatus based on Permendagri no. 1317. The implementation of the inflation control road map for programs that are not yet optimal implemented in Sukabumi City was complained about by the fourth informant. Where budget constraints are suspected to be the cause. The inflation control road map must be able to be implemented in the Sukabumi City TPID work program according to the first informant and the sixth informant, because it has been determined by the West Java TPID to be a reference, only the program implemented to meet the targets on the inflation road map deserves further study because It is left to each region to implement it according to the characteristics of their region. The first informant also stated a similar thing, here is a snippet of his answer: "It must be able to be implemented because it has become a provision for all TPIDs, because the road map is a reference for TPID work in each region, however, the type of program carried out varies according to regional needs."

2. Resource

The human resources at TPID Sukabumi City were considered to be of sufficient quantity and quality by all informants. TPID membership is tied to a position in the service, at the level of head of service or at least head of field. The first informant explained at length his opinion regarding the quality and quantity of human resources at TPID, namely: “TPID membership is bound by daily position in officialdom (*ex officio*). TPID membership is tied to the official position, namely Echelon 2, while in daily activities the mainstay is the staff who directly handle that area, so there is a lack of accuracy between those who take part in coordination meetings with daily and policy actors. Rotation in service positions is very influential in the composition of TPID members. This means that there are new or continually changing TPID members. So the abilities of TPID members are not standardized, depending on the placement of personnel in the service. in the latest membership structure, there is the formation of a food task force. So the MUSPIDA elements that were initially registered as TPID members are currently not in the TPID

membership, but are included as members of the food task force. TPID members' understanding of inflation is still varied and limited. "At BI the focus of controlling inflation in the regions is on GNPIP (National Movement to Control Food Inflation) even though the factors that influence inflation are more than that."

The problem of job rotation which has the potential to become an obstacle to the quantity of human resources at TPID was also raised by the second informant. Mutations and rotations are normal things found in bureaucracy, which are entirely within the authority of regional leaders. TPID does not have the ability to select or detain its members regarding this condition, explained the second informant. According to the sixth informant, the expertise of TPID members in their field has been tested in the official service because TPID members are also government officials. Opinions regarding the integrity and competence of the human resources involved in TPID according to the informants are good. A fairly complete answer was given by the sixth informant, namely: "The competency and integrity of human resources are also good and increasingly competitive in recent years with the presence of evaluations of inflation control activities from the Ministry of Home Affairs, including the provision of rewards and punishments for regional heads who are deemed successful or less able to implement inflation control programs in their regions."

A critical point was expressed by the second informant who said that if TPID membership was tied to a position at the level of head of department, in the implementation of inflation control it was the staff who went to the field. According to the first informant, TPID membership can suddenly change due to rotation or transfer in official positions. If this happens, then the TPID membership decree does not need to be revised because it is in accordance with the presidential decree, the decree for establishing TPID in a district/city only needs to be made once. In 2024, TPID will experience a substantive change in membership, namely the involvement of the Head of the State Treasury Office (KPPN), resulting in the publication of the latest revision of the formation of TPID in Sukabumi City in January (decree attached). One way to increase the competence of organizational members is through training. Informants from outside the Sukabumi City TPID members, namely the fifth and sixth informants, stated that they did not know much about the training activities organized by the Sukabumi City TPID for their members. According to their observations, the material presented at the routine coordination meeting with TPID West Java Province was quite relevant to knowledge about inflation and economic phenomena developing in society. The transfer of knowledge related to inflation can be absorbed through presentations from competent sources in their fields at each coordination meeting. The second to fourth informants admitted that technical or non-technical training had not been held for Sukabumi City TPID members. More precisely, the third informant stated that: "There is no special training but the Team adds insight and knowledge by coordinating and consulting with the provincial TPID and TPIN"

According to the first respondent, TPIN once held capacity building activities. Meanwhile, Sukabumi City is carrying out a comparative study of TPID members to other areas that are considered successful in controlling inflation, such as Banyuwangi Regency and DKI Jakarta Province.

The availability of facilities and infrastructure was not sufficient to support TPID activities, admitted by the first informant. The first respondent clearly explained the following regarding the facilities and infrastructure at TPID: "TPID does not have special facilities and infrastructure but rather concerns the SKPD members of TPID. The results of the comparative study include that areas that have successfully controlled inflation have good infrastructure and are producing areas (Banyuwangi). Meanwhile, DKI Jakarta has adequate financial support, such as having a wholesale market, many BUMDs (factors controlling the distribution and price chains) so that SKPDs are only tasked with contributing data needs (agricultural data, food balance, deficit/surplus commodities). "Meanwhile, Sukabumi City does not yet have this, so the function of purchasing or controlling market prices has to be carried out by SKPD with the available budget."

Contrary to the opinion of the first informant, the third informant considered that the facilities and infrastructure to support TPID activities were sufficient. Meanwhile, similar answers were obtained from the second and fourth respondents, that the facilities and infrastructure to support TPID activities were obtained from their respective SKPD.

Funding for the implementation of district/city TPID tasks based on Minister of Home Affairs Decree Number 500.05-8135 of 2017 is borne by the APBD and other legitimate sources based on the provisions of statutory regulations. Budget limitations due to the SOTK form, which is a combination of several functions, were an obstacle in carrying out TPID duties, which was complained about by the first informant. The following is an excerpt from the answer from the first informant regarding the TPID budget: "The budget for the TPID secretariat to hold meetings is in the Economic Section with a budget allocation of IDR 50 million for meeting activities which is still considered insufficient. The budget for controlling inflation is spread across each TPID member SKPD. "The budget is not specifically recorded for inflation control but is related to activities in SKPD that are appropriate to support inflation control."

The second informant stated bluntly that there was no special budget for controlling inflation from his agency. In 2024 there will be an increase in performance to support TPID activities, namely by providing a budget for official travel within the city. In relation to inflation control activities that have been carried out so far, this is to act as a liaison between goods providers and DKP3, as the agency that has a budget for subsidies. The second informant's further explanation was: "Usage of the budget for goods subsidies in cheap market activities at certain moments is provided by the West Java Province Department of Industry and Trade, for example for subsidized cheap market operations. Sukabumi City Diskumindag acts as coordinator of providing recipient data (obtained from DTKS social services), confirmation to the local sub-district area, to distribution by name by address."

The fourth informant also experienced the same thing, he said: "TPID does not have a special budget. "So the inflation control policy is related to the budget in each SKPD and the capacity of the regional budget."

In the agency where the fourth informant works, the use of the official budget in the context of controlling inflation is for organizing the Cheap Food Movement (GPM). The existing budget is utilized optimally to organize GPM that reaches the wider community. According to the third

informant, an additional budget is needed to deal with inflation directly, such as activities aimed at increasing price affordability and availability of food supplies. Because the focus of the budget for handling inflation is currently focused on handling smooth distribution. The use of the budget to support the smooth distribution of goods is considered to be quite efficient, said the third informant. Regarding the budget, the fifth and sixth informants stated that in accordance with the regulations for establishing TPIDs in districts/cities, the budget for carrying out TPID duties was provided from the respective regional APBD and from BI. In more detail, the following is an excerpt from an interview with the sixth respondent regarding budget availability: "In accordance with regulations, the budget for carrying out TPID duties is provided by the regional government, related parties and Indonesian banks. "So it depends on how the regional budget allocation is provided for inflation control activities."

Meanwhile, regarding the use of the available budget, the fifth informant gave examples of cases that had occurred, namely: "The available budget to support TPID activities is already available in the regional government APBD, but if it is deemed necessary the central government will issue a policy to specifically handle inflation, such as in 2022, after an increase in subsidized fuel prices occurred, the central government issued a Minister of Finance regulation and circular letter "Minister of Home Affairs to all Governors, Regents and Mayors to use Unexpected Assistance Expenditures to control inflation in the regions"

3. Characteristics of the Implementing Organization

Informants' responses regarding questions about the existence of written SOPs regarding the implementation of inflation control policies as members of the TPID, in general the informants said that the existing SOPs were SOPs in their respective SKPDs related to inflation control activities for which they were responsible. Not only technical, non-technical activities in TPID are still attached to positions in the service. The first informant further provided the following information: "TPID decisions or policies are attached to the Mayor's authority as chairman of TPID, using Regional Secretariat administrative documents. Sukabumi City TPID does not have its own official letterhead so that the inflation control activities carried out are difficult to separate between duties as TPID and main duties as SKPD. For example, the TPID secretariat is held by the Economics Section, socialization of inflation control activities is carried out by related agencies such as Kominfo and Bappeda. TPID status tends to only be used during meetings and internal communications. It is difficult to separate the position as TPID from daily positions in the official service. "So far, TPID has tended to operate in the field of coordination or meetings, but in its policy it returns to each of the main tasks and functions of the service."

The fourth informant stated that he did not have an SOP for involvement in TPID activities in his agency. The opinion of the sixth informant confirms the existence of written SOPs for implementing inflation control policies, namely: "There is no SOP yet. "Because the implementation of inflation control activities is in each SKPD according to their respective domains, the SOP for implementation also seems to be related to the SOP in that SKPD."

4. Attitude of Implementers

TPID membership is dominated by government officials, therefore it is ensured that the government fully supports the policies formulated to control inflation. Questions about the attitude and commitment of implementers towards the implementation of inflation control policies received positive responses from all informants. The hope of the fifth informant is that policy implementers will not think that inflation is just a number that must be kept as low as possible. There is a further meaning that must be understood behind the inflation figures that are occurring, here is a quote from the answer from the fifth informant: "Inflation is not just a number, but a matter of maintaining people's welfare. Poverty, unemployment, economic performance are closely related to inflation, because inflation is not just a matter of numbers but you have to look more closely at the impact it has."

Meanwhile, similar statements were given by the first and fourth informants. They linked the attitudes of TPID members to their responsibilities in the service. More precisely, the first informant thinks as follows: "The attitude of the implementers who are members of TPID are fully committed to implementing inflation control policies according to their related duties as their official responsibilities. "TPID meetings can be delegated from members (echelon 2) to staff in their departments who are directly related to daily responsibilities."

According to the third informant, the routine inflation control activity program has been implemented according to the planning documents in each SKPD so that it is relatively acceptable to its members. There was increased support from regional leaders this year compared to the previous period for implementing inflation control policies, said the fourth informant.

The dominant obstacle complained about by informants in implementing inflation control policies is budget limitations. Apart from that, there are also those who feel they are experiencing problems from a technical perspective, such as implementation instructions that are not in accordance with field conditions and inaccurate data on food aid recipients. Quotes from interviews with the first informant regarding the obstacles and barriers faced by TPID Sukabumi City are: "The main obstacle is felt from the budget side. Because inflation is a priority program but no special budget is provided to control it. Infrastructure in Sukabumi City is also not as good as other areas which have wholesale markets and food BUMDs, so controlling inflation in Sukabumi City still tends to be left to market mechanisms (the existence of TPID can be ignored). Inflation control by TPID in Sukabumi City is still a "fire extinguisher". In terms of goods production in Sukabumi City, it is always in deficit so it has to rely on supplies from other regions, therefore it is important to collaborate with other regions. Sukabumi City already has an MoU with Sukabumi Regency and other regions but not in terms of commodities. "Ideally, Sukabumi City would have a main market or something similar so that monitoring the entry and exit of goods would be easier to monitor."

Based on the second informant's account, the obstacle of the lack of legal power that his agency has to control market prices is considered to be the main obstacle experienced, a more complete answer is as follows: "The obstacle is that there are no regulations that can control market prices, so they cannot be influenced by the Ministry of Finance and Trade. Unlike in Bapanas there are provisions for HET (must be the same) but the Diskumindag can only carry

out orders without having the ability to issue policies, such as in the case of cooking oil shortages where the Diskumindag has taken great pains to carry out orders but in the end it turns into a problem and is called to the Prosecutor's Office. The next obstacle is limited data availability and inaccurate data relating to inflation control activities so that it does not correspond to field conditions, especially for data on food distributors. "Apart from that, the obstacle is that Sukabumi City does not have a main market or a special place to monitor goods coming in and out, so if data is needed regarding the availability of goods, you have to search widely."

The monitoring function of a policy is carried out to ensure that the implementation process is carried out in accordance with planning. Likewise, inflation control activities are monitored periodically by the West Java Province TPID, TPIN, Ministry of Home Affairs and Bank Indonesia. At the Sukabumi City level itself, every month the Economy and Development Section provides a report on inflation conditions to the Mayor. Daily activity monitoring is also carried out in the TPID WhatsApp/WA group. The complete answer from the first informant regarding monitoring activities carried out on TPID was: "TPID reports to TPIN every quarter. "There is TPIN's assessment of TPID's performance, such as how many meetings were chaired by the regional head/Regional Secretary, whether there were any policies issued regarding inflation (3 kg LPG price, subsidized fertilizer prices)."

Meanwhile, the third respondent gave the following answer: "Monitoring is carried out in stages every quarter, either provincially or nationally via the application. "The monitoring process is carried out on the implementation of inflation control activities through reporting progress on realization of both budget and performance on a quarterly basis."

The use of the budget for TPID activities did not escape the supervision of the Inspectorate and BPKP according to the third informant, where in the process the BPKP went directly to the Sukabumi City TPID secretariat. Confirmation from the sixth informant regarding the monitoring process which is carried out periodically through routine coordination meetings held to discuss reports on the results of TPID activities and in stages.

5. Communication between related organizations and implementation activities

Researchers reviewed the communication that occurs within the TPID organization through 4 variables, namely clear division of tasks, procedures for coordination and communication between members, ways to socialize policy results, and finally the condition of the organizational structure. A clear division of tasks between agencies that are part of the TPID is absolutely necessary so that communication runs smoothly, and coordination is in harmony. The answers from all informants stated that the division of tasks between members in the TPID was quite clear because it was related to the daily duties and functions of the service. The response from the first informant to this question was quite complete along with examples of coordination between TPID members in accordance with their respective duties, here are excerpts from the interview: "There is a clear division of tasks, each TPID member carries out tasks that focus on the core tasks of their respective services, such as Diskumindag for controlling prices of traded goods, DKP3 for production, Bulog regarding stock control. The sub-district head determines the location for GPM implementation and facilitates area availability. It is difficult to separate the

control actions carried out from the position as TPID or as the main function of the service. There is no clear distinction in inflation control measures within positions in the service. For interventions related to central government reserves (CPP), the recipient data in Sukabumi City is around 2000 people, the data is based on data from the Ministry of Social Affairs. Bapanas assigned Bulog to distribute it directly to recipients. DKP 3 and Dinsos are tasked with monitoring."

The division of tasks is quite clear because it relates to the main duties and functions of the department, however, according to the second informant, there is still overlap in implementation, such as in data monitoring activities. In accordance with its main duties, Diskumindag monitors and reports price changes in the market every day. However, it turns out that there are other agencies that also carry out price monitoring activities and often the prices reported for the same commodity are different. The second informant felt quite disturbed if the results of the data collection carried out by his agency were questioned because of the differences that occurred. Even though price conditions in the market move dynamically over time and trader respondents are the data source. The fifth and sixth informants stated that the division of tasks between TPID members was regulated in the applicable regulations. In the current internet era, communication through communication media has become a necessity of life, even in organizations like TPID. For smooth communication, interaction in the TPID WhatsApp group is the main choice, internet coverage which supports all areas of Sukabumi City is a supporting factor that encourages smooth communication. TPID meetings are also held regularly or at any time if necessary and also serve as a way to coordinate the implementation of activities at TPID. This also includes coordination meetings with provincial TPIN and TPID which use video conferencing media. The presence of communication technology makes coordination between regions easier because it shortens the distance and travel time to the meeting place and makes travel costs more efficient. The mechanism for holding meetings at TPID Sukabumi City was explained by the first informant as follows: "For routine meeting agendas, the TPID secretariat makes invitations or at the initiative of members who feel that coordination is needed. Usually coordination is carried out at certain moments that are considered to influence economic conditions, such as religious holidays and New Year. Meetings are held as needed, in 2023 for example the number of meetings held will reach more than 60 times. "Communication is quite good through the WA group, which runs responsively every day, including reporting commodity prices."

The next question asked by the researcher to the informants obtained various responses. The informants' experiences while interacting at TPID resulted in different answers to questions about the advantages and disadvantages of the TPID organizational structure. These various answers further complement the researcher's knowledge regarding the TPID organization in Sukabumi City. The advantage mentioned by the second and sixth informants is that advances in communication technology make it possible for communication and coordination between parties involved in TPID or TPIN to coordinate at any time, so that the TPID organizational structure can be responsive to the latest economic phenomena. Meanwhile, the fourth informant answered that the advantage of the current conditions in the TPID organization is that the government pays attention to the importance of controlling inflation much better, making it easier

for TPID activities. According to the first and fourth informants, the weakness of the TPID organizational structure is the budget problem. A more complete explanation from the first informant is as follows: "TPID is asked to control inflation, even though the types of activities that can be carried out still involve those listed in the DPA (budget). Even though inflation is an outcome, an accumulation of many things that happen in the economy, so it is not certain that the impact of the things that intervene in TPID activities can immediately be seen at that time. TPID's ability to control inflation is seen as limited, only in the form of market operations, cheap food promotions which are like "fire extinguishers" in responding to events in society, have not been able to become problem solving."

In line with the opinion above, the fifth informant also said the following: "The weakness at the district/city level in controlling inflation is still focused on controlling food prices, especially basic necessities because this is the easiest thing to monitor and can be intervened in for many reasons. For the areas above, such as control by companies which may do this starting from the provincial level, or monetary matters controlled by BI. The presence of TPID, which in terms of implementing inflation control policies is carried out by the relevant SKPD, tends to act as a regulator. "Meanwhile, price control is still predominantly left to market mechanisms."

6. Social, Economic and Political Environment

The public's response to inflation is still limited to a reaction to rising prices on the market. As explained by the sixth informant: "It seems the general public still doesn't understand inflation. People tend to refer to inflation when there is an increase in prices and a shortage of goods/services."

The fifth informant's account of the public's response to inflation control policies is as follows: "The public may not be aware of the inflation control policies that have been implemented recently, but the impact of the policy formulations issued by TPID, such as pressure on the planned fuel tax increase, which, although not carried out directly by TPID Sukabumi City, is the impact of the pressure exerted TPID West Java Province succeeded in delaying the plan. The considerations given by TPID regarding the negative impact of the increase in fuel tax on the purchasing power of the general public, were able to convince the parties concerned."

An in-depth explanation from the first respondent regarding the community's response was: "The public tends not to know about TPID activities. What the public understands is the problem of rising prices or scarcity of goods. for example, market operations are carried out according to needs. Moreover, if there is market turmoil in a commodity, the SKPD is responsible for coordinating with Bulog to organize the GPM. Usually technical coordination is carried out by Diskumindag and DKP3. TPID should play a more important role in educating the public about policies regarding the economy so that the public does not become overly anxious about responding to the economic phenomena that occur and is able to reduce the anxiety that occurs."

According to the second and third informants, the current needs of society regarding inflation control policies are increasing cheap market operations and significantly reducing food prices. The sixth informant had the following opinion: "People need price stability (not fluctuating) and supply stability."

Easy access to obtain necessary goods and prices that are relatively affordable for people's purchasing power are the opinions of the fourth and fifth informants regarding the community's need for inflation control policies.

The geographical location of Sukabumi City, which is not too large, provides its own advantages, making it easier to coordinate and distribute goods, which is a supporting factor for the success of the inflation control policy in Sukabumi City, according to the first informant. Another opinion was expressed by the third informant, namely: "The technical SKPD implementing activities that directly targets inflation control can carry out activities according to the targets set and have a real impact on controlling inflation because the intervention program has been synchronized in the budget of each relevant SKPD."

Another informant said that through TPID the government could act as a cooperation or regulatory regulator, so that it could reduce the subsidy budget for community needs. According to the sixth informant, routine evaluations from the Ministry of Home Affairs are a supporting factor in the success of controlling inflation, because indications of inflation fluctuations can be anticipated early. Meanwhile, the factor inhibiting policy according to the sixth informant is that support for infrastructure facilities is not evenly distributed in all regions, meaning that the implementation of inflation control policies can differ in the response and speed of the intervention program being implemented. The third and fourth informants each believed that data difficulties for monitoring and evaluation and budgeting were factors inhibiting the success of inflation control policies. The answer from the first informant to the same question was: "The inhibiting factors are that first, Sukabumi City is a consumer area that does not have warehouses because so far the position of goods has been separated in several locations. Second, Sukabumi City does not have a special BUMD that handles agriculture. As a consumer city, price creation in Sukabumi City is relatively easily influenced by conditions in external areas. Third, the large number of work teams formed with the same people sitting as members also poses a challenge to the effectiveness of TPID activities."

One thing that is different from the second informant's response regarding factors inhibiting inflation policy apart from those mentioned by the previous informants is the need to control illegal levies carried out by thugs in the market.

Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion, the conclusions are as follows:

1. The implementation of inflation control policies in Sukabumi City is quite effective, this is because:
 - a) Policy standards and targets already have a written basis that is clear and measurable. The Sukabumi City regional inflation control roadmap work program has been prepared and integrated into the work plan of each SKPD responsible for activities.
 - b) Implementation of inflation control policies in Sukabumi City is still focused on efforts to ensure price affordability, such as daily food price monitoring activities, Cheap Food Promotion (GPM), Subsidized Market Operations, distribution of food aid. Meanwhile,

- the other three key strategies for controlling inflation, namely affordability of supply, smooth distribution and effective communication, have not received balanced attention.
- c) Membership in TPID is binding on official positions (*ex officio*), while field implementers of the inflation control program involve all SKPD staff who are responsible for the program. Position rotation and transfers affect membership in the Sukabumi City TPID. Knowledge about inflation policy is mainly obtained from material presented in coordination meetings. The human resources who serve as TPID members are considered to be sufficiently qualified and competent in carrying out their duties.
 - d) The budget and facilities and infrastructure to support the implementation of inflation control policies are available from the SKPD responsible for the program, however, it is felt that they are still limited.
 - e) The characteristics of the TPID organization show that the division of tasks and functions is clearly structured in legal provisions and is adhered to by its members. Guidelines for implementing policy implementation are in each SKPD according to the type of program being implemented.
 - f) Full support and commitment from the regional government is provided for the successful implementation of inflation control policies, especially with the evaluation pattern from the central government which provides rewards and punishments for the performance of regional heads in controlling inflation.
 - g) Advances in communication technology support smooth coordination between related organizations and implementation activities of inflation control policies. The distribution of duties and functions of each member has been determined in the applicable legal regulations. The monitoring, evaluation, control and socialization processes are carried out regularly through reports and regular meetings, either face to face or online.
 - h) The social, economic and political environment has a positive influence on the implementation of current inflation control policies. Public knowledge regarding inflation control is still limited to reactions when product price fluctuations occur.
2. The main obstacle in implementing the inflation control policy in Sukabumi City is the limited budget, apart from that the infrastructure facilities to support the implementation of the inflation control program are also not yet optimal, the preparation of the inflation control program has not been fully structured, and the legitimacy of the existence of the TPID to carry out inflation control measures is not yet complete. fully recognized.

Suggestion

Theoretical Aspects

It is realized that there are still opportunities for deficiencies and weaknesses in the research process of implementing inflation control policies in Sukabumi City by researchers. The researcher's limited time in approaching informants and the researcher's ability to dig up information are believed to be quite influential factors in the shortcomings that occur. Economic

phenomena will move dynamically as times change. There is still much that can be developed regarding inflation control policies, as well as their implementation.

This research is still limited to analyzing the implementation of inflation control policies in Sukabumi City in terms of Van Meter and Von Horn. Economic phenomena will continue to move along with human life and implementation is not the end of the public policy cycle, so research on inflation control policies is still very relevant for further exploration. It is hoped that in-depth studies on similar themes will be developed by other researchers. Hopefully this research is worthy of being used as a reference for further research related to inflation control policies. In order to enrich the treasures of knowledge, it is recommended that researchers who want to carry out similar studies review them using different theories.

Practical Aspects

1. The implementation of inflation control policies in Sukabumi City needs to continue to be developed in accordance with developments in economic phenomena occurring in the field.
2. Providing a more comprehensive understanding of inflation to all parties involved in implementing the inflation control program, either in the form of training or outreach
3. An inflation control program that is planned and relevant to problems in society is something that needs to be prepared immediately.
4. Adequate budget support is needed to finance more efficient inflation control intervention programs to be able to achieve targets.
5. The development of infrastructure to support economic activities, such as organized shopping centers, smooth transportation facilities and reliable goods storage warehouses will have a positive impact on controlling inflation in Sukabumi City.

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